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Evaluation 3 of "Selecting the Most Effective Nudge: Evidence from a Large-Scale Experiment on Immunization"

Evaluator 3

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Evaluation of

"Selecting the Most Effective Nudge: Evidence from a Large-Scale Experiment on Immunization" (via <https://web.stanford.edu/~arungc/TVA.pdf>, version from June 18, 2024)

for the Unjournal

Overall Summary: The paper presents a technique to select a (best) policy from a large factorial design, including, for example, various dosages of a treatment that can be ordered with respect to their intensity. Essentially, the technique aims to aggregate variants of a treatment that yield (effectively) the same effect, thereby reducing the dimensionality of possible options, and consequently increasing power and precision of estimates for the effect sizes of truly effective treatments. The technique is applied to a large-scale experiment, where 75 policies are tested that involve combinations of reminders, incentives, and local ambassadors, with the aim of increasing the number of child immunizations in the state of Haryana (India). A combination of ambassadors and reminders is leading to the largest impact when paired with incentives; without incentives, a very similar combination is identified as the most cost-effective one (any form of ambassador paired with reminders).

The method: The method is mostly a clever combination of already existing -- sometimes more, sometimes less -- established methods. The true merit of the paper with respect to the method lies in identifying those, putting them together, and finally showing that under "strong assumptions" (p. 34), the method "rules out some of the cases where model-selection leads to invalid inferences" (p. 34), and produces estimates that are consistent and asymptotically normal. Specifically, in a first step, all treatments and their interactions are included in a regression via marginal effects (known from a staggered design, for example). Then, a LASSO is performed. This, however, cannot be performed directly on the marginal effects due to the high correlations. The authors identify a "Puffer transformation" due to Jia and Rohe (2015) as a suitable solution. The LASSO then identifies marginal effects that are effective, and others that are not (essentially based on their p-values). Only then the variant aggregation starts, such that dosages that do not lead to different effects (according to the LASSO) are grouped. Treatments that have no effect whatsoever are either "pooled or pruned (pooled with control)". Scientifically, I am a bit unsure whether this should be allowed; a discussion seems warranted. It is obviously principled and data-driven, but conceptually, it seems wrong to me.

Regarding the asymptotic results, I cannot fully assess them, as going through all the proofs seems to be out of scope considered that this is not the core of my work. Yet, it is clear that asymptotic arguments and asymptotic results imply that they need not always hold (as they depend on N). Hence, a limitation of the "existence" result (the correct support of effective marginal effects is indeed selected by the LASSO), as well as consistency and normality results is that applicability is not universal. The authors provide guidance by presenting simulations showing that normality is approximately fulfilled in the given setting. Whether or not the strong assumptions

are likely to be fulfilled in different settings will remain a judgement call; in particular, finding a penalty sequence for the LASSO that fulfills Assumption 5 seems non-trivial. Unless I've missed it, there seems no guidance in that respect (even though there are robustness checks).

A suggestion would thus be to provide some more intuition about the settings in which the assumptions can be expected to hold; after all, the present paper may use thousands of data points, which is not necessarily representative. Unless there will be no software implementation, I am unsure how much practitioners will adapt the technique; the Jia and Rohe (2015) correction for correlated regressors seems technical, too, and so does the Andrews et al. (2021)-correction for the winner's curse. As a final comment, it is to be seen whether adaptive designs or the current design approach will become more prevalent in the future.

The field intervention: The field data result from a collaboration with the government of the state of Haryana in India, with the objective to improve immunization rates. The data consists of about 300,000 children, and about 60,000 households satisfied the eligibility criterion of having children between the ages of 12 to 18 months. While this allows for an impressive study, by now, the innovation of the tested tools is somewhat limited. That is: All tested interventions have been studied before, including by the authors, and including in this very same dataset (Banerjee et al., 2019, "Using Gossips to Spread Information: Theory and Evidence from Two Randomized Controlled Trials"). This fact is communicated only on page 28, which is a bit late for my taste. Yet, previous research has ignored interactions between the treatments (at least of the full set considered here), which is to be seen as the main contribution of the field data. The tested interventions are: i) incentives (in the combinations low/high and flat/increasing with every immunization shot, where low corresponded to about 500 minutes of mobile phone talk time for all five immunization shots), ii) SMS reminders (no reminder, reminders to 33% of parents, reminders to 66% of parents), and iii) ambassadors (randomly selected, information hubs identified by fellow villagers, trusted advisors regarding agriculture and health identified by fellow villagers, trusted advisors who were identified as information hubs). In addition to informing about possible interaction effects, and despite not being particularly innovative with respect to the tested interventions from today's perspective (baseline data was collected mid 2016), the study can contribute to our understanding of the relative merit of the interventions, which is also extremely valuable, even today (see Figure 4 for the results; only high incentives (increasing with every vaccine) are effective, and this to a similar degree than relying on ambassadors - even more than on trusted ambassadors).

Comments on the field intervention: - On page 27, the authors refer to an online appendix, in which they report about their data quality checks. In the main text, they describe the data quality as "excellent". In the appendix (p. 92), we learn that childrens' names and date of birth were accurate in 80% of the checks, and that there were "almost no" fake child records, which is, however, not quantified. Finally, for 71% of the children, the vaccines overlapped completely. I work with field data myself, and I know that these number are realistic, but objectively, this cannot be described as excellent. Administrative data from Denmark or Norway is excellent, but 71% overlapping vaccines certainly are not. As the errors are not different across treatment groups, results

should be unaffected, though. - Substitution effects are analyzed in an online appendix, but the tables are in landscape format, but the relevant pages are not, and hence about half of the tables/pages seem to be cut. As a result, notes are not informative, as half of the information is missing; several columns seem to be missing, too. The content of the table remains cryptic, making it difficult to assess whether the incentive-effects are actually substitution effects, or are indeed new immunization shots. It remains unclear how the dependent variable and the regressors are coded (i.e., whether the regressions predict showing up for an immunization under a given incentive scheme and having been immunized somewhere else before (as the main text would suggest), or whether the regressions predict showing up for immunization despite not being in the register (as the Table headings suggest)). Yet, what can be seen looks innocent, in the sense that the share is not different across treatments, and hence there is hope that this is also true for the missing columns. However, the control means look incredibly high (up to .69) should the dependent variable really equal 1 if a child is not in the register. If this were the case, this issue should deserve more discussion. - Section 4 could benefit from proofreading and streamlining. At the end, as a reader one is confused which sub-set of the data is finally analyzed. - According to the pre-registration/pre-analysis plan (first mentioned on page 29, footnote 27 -- also a bit late), the authors were interested in (some) previously not analyzed interaction effects between incentives, reminders and ambassadors (called "gossip" in Banerjee et al., 2019). A systematic approach like the current one did not seem to be the plan, however, not even in the updated pre-registration from 2018. The authors could comment on this change (which is completely legitimate, in my view).